

Table 1: Q-Set Statements		
Statement No.	Statement	The Rationale for Including the Statement in the Final Q-Set
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting client concerns about portfolio performance.	Does the firm share investors' concerns over markets and performance (service and fiduciary logics)? Or is ancillary planning used to distract from these issues and provide a means to gather more assets and/or keep clients from leaving the advisory program (sales logics)?
2	Management expresses concern and/or interest about individual PCA investor portfolio performance.	Does management care about their clients' investment performance (service logics and fiduciary logics), or does the drive for sales (sales logics) dominate?
3	Because of my workload, I sometimes worry about the possibility of important things falling through the cracks.	Does the drive for 'getting the numbers' (sales logics) overshadow the importance of providing good quality service (service logics with possible implications for fiduciary logics too)?
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I didn't have specific, measurable performance expectations.	Does the effect on motivation from having sales targets, quotas, or goals (sales logics) detract from an advisor's productivity, feelings of autonomy, relatedness, and competence (fiduciary logics and service logics)?
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investors succeed as possible.	This illuminates possible tension between PCAs' commitment to serve others (service logics and fiduciary logics) and self-interests (sales logics).
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed.	Are advisors self-serving (sales logics), or do they hold altruistic beliefs (service logics and fiduciary logics)?
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my boss.	Does the desire to please the boss motivate an unchecked desire to 'make the numbers' (sales logics), leading to behavior that can conflict with advisors' fiduciary obligations (fiduciary logics)?
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succeed.	Exposes possible tension between teamwork (service logics) and self-interests (sales logics).
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the damage it may cause to their relationship with the referring FC.	Do conflicts of interest arise because advisors sometimes pander to referring FCs to maintain sales levels (sales logics) rather than ensuring the advisory service is in clients' best interest (fiduciary logic)?
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad financial planning topics.	Is ancillary planning intended to identify outside assets and persuade investors to transfer them to the firm (sales logics) or primarily to provide comprehensive services and exercise their fiduciary duty (service logics and sales logics)?
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the performance of their investments.	If performance matters most to clients, then advisors, as fiduciaries (fiduciary logics), redirecting the conversation to other planning topics in an attempt to maintain client enrollment numbers (sales logics) poses an ethical conflict.
12	I must keep in mind, as important, that clients equate trading activity with progress.	Do advisors pander to clients to keep them enrolled (sales logics) by recommending unnecessary trading (fiduciary logics), realizing that clients believe that lack of trading activity is a reason for poor performance?
13	I must keep in mind as important, that clients equate inactivity with their advisor 'being asleep at the wheel'.	Clients sometimes believe their advisor is inattentive if trading activity is low and consider leaving (sales logics). Even if no activity is warranted (fiduciary logics), advisors may feel pressured to trade to maintain appearances.

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14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	Do advisors feel compliance requirements (fiduciary logics) hamper their sales (sales logics) efforts too much?
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and single-topic solutions provides a desirable way to motivate me.	Do advisors like having numerical targets? What are the implications regarding exercising one's fiduciary duty (fiduciary logics) alongside the need to attain sales targets (sales logics)?
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not reasonable, it is demotivating.	If the targets are unfair, morale may be adversely affected. Moreover, advisors may feel pressure to cut ethical corners (fiduciary logics) to ensure they achieve the targets (sales logics).
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box' mentality where the quality of the work can be secondary to getting it done.	Do conflicts of interest arise because of the need to achieve a certain quantity of deliverables (sales logics) versus focusing on quality and clients' best interest (fiduciary logics)?
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may sometimes make me think twice about disagreeing with a client or delivering news that might be perceived negatively.	Do CPS targets create conflicts of interest with clients because of advisors' reluctance to convey unwelcome but essential information (fiduciary logics) for fear of inducing a low CPS score (sales logics)?
19	As long as I were well paid, if I didn't have performance targets, I would be motivated anyway because I find the work I do is important and personally gratifying.	To what degree are advisors intrinsically motivated (service logics) versus extrinsically motivated (sales logics)?
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specific, measurable performance targets.	To what degree are advisors extrinsically motivated (sales logics) versus motivated to serve others (service logics)?
21	If we were really 'looking through client's eyes', it would be best to tie bonuses to how well clients are doing toward achieving their financial goals.	Does the importance of clients achieving their financial goals (service logics) trump other considerations, such as advisors attaining their sales goals (sales logics)?
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and single-topic solutions clients receive.	Do advisors believe they are being incented to accomplish relatively ancillary activities (sales logics) versus focusing on relevant aspects of client investing success (fiduciary logics)?
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company performed.	Do advisors connect their personal success with that of the company? The tension is between self-interest (sales logics and service (service logics) to the organization.
24	Sometimes an employees' contribution to the firm's business is not fully reflected in their production numbers.	How do advisors feel about the performance evaluation process? Do 'the numbers' (sales logics) tell the whole story? Or does providing less easily quantifiable service (service logics) count too?
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they would receive adequate attention if they knew I have responsibility for 185 clients.	What are the consequences if advisors 1) need to attract and retain new investors but are afraid of losing business if they share how many clients they have (sales logics), 2) have too many clients, which leads to difficulties in maintaining service quality (service logics) and 3) advisors lie or sidestep answering this question (fiduciary logics).
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and which ones to remove from my practice.	What are the consequences when advisors' sense of professional autonomy (fiduciary logics) is weak, such that they are forced to work with clients (sales logics) for whom the offer is not in the client's best interest?

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27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose focus on sales may require me to work with clients for whom the PCIA offer may not be well suited.	What are the consequences of advisors feeling forced to work with clients where the advisory program is not in their best interest (fiduciary logics) versus the need to accept business from referring FCs so that advisors achieve sales goals (sales logics)?
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cover the same branch locations.	Does having too many advisors responsible for the same territory lead advisors to cut ethical corners (fiduciary logics) by overpromising and under-delivering to internal and external clients to gain a business edge (sales logics)?
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to compromise my ethical standards at least a little.	Does the influence of FCs (sales logics) lead to advisors cutting ethical corners to be successful (fiduciary logics)?
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how well I serve clients.	Do extrinsic factors associated with the targets, goals, and quotas (sales logics) support how well advisors serve (service logics) clients?
31	As a fiduciary, I have too many clients to serve them all well.	Does an unsustainably large workload result in a conflict of interest because advisors must choose between providing good service (service logics) versus rationalizing providing lesser quality service and diminished fiduciary effectiveness (fiduciary logics) to continue to grow their practice to a theoretically unlimited number (sales logics)?
32	PCAs should be allowed to 'soft-close' and /or reopen their practice as desired based upon workload.	What is the importance of self-determination and autonomy versus the degree to which advisors are required to continue to grow their practices (sales logics) regardless of their ability to properly serve (service logics) their clients as professionals having fiduciary duty (fiduciary logics)?
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature of their workload because it might discourage getting new referrals.	Do unmanageably large advisor practice sizes create conflicts of interest because of the need to sell? The tension is between the need to continue to enroll clients regardless of capacity (sales logics) and the fiduciary requirement to be transparent (fiduciary logics).
34	It is awkward when a client asks, "How often do you review my investments?" because the real answer may not seem like it would be often enough to them.	What is the impact of having excessive clients on the ability of advisors to adequately serve their clients and the ethics of avoiding such questions or, worse, to hedge or lie? This statement places the need to sell (sales logics) in tension with the ability to provide adequate levels of service (service logics) along with the need for transparency associated with fiduciary duty (fiduciary logics).
35	My success depends on getting new referrals from FCs so I should be careful not to contradict or alienate them.	To what extent do advisors have to pander to the wishes of FCs (sales logics), wherein doing so may have a bearing on working in the firm's or client's best interest (fiduciary logics)?
36	I feel my role is sales-oriented because I have to sell myself to FCs and sell myself to clients.	This statement is intended to understand the degree to which sales is the dominant logic.